

PREDICTING FLUTIST ONSET TIMING IN DUET PERFORMANCE: A MULTIMODAL ANALYSIS OF GESTURE AND BREATH CUES

Jaeran Choi Taegyun Kwon Juhan Nam
Graduate School of Culture Technology, KAIST, South Korea

{jaeran.choi, ilcobo2, juhan.nam}@kaist.ac.kr

ABSTRACT

In ensemble performances, musicians use gesture and breath cues to synchronize their initial notes at the beginning of a piece, but the precise relationship between these cues and onset timing remains under-explored. This study investigates how flutists' gesture and breath cues encode the timing information for the initial note onset. This research consists of four components: (1) Collection of a cue dataset containing synchronized video and audio recordings of flute-piano duets, (2) Identification of cue candidate points through facial movement curves and breath onset-offset analysis, (3) Verification of predicted onset accuracy using linear regression on these cues compared to human onset asynchronies and (4) Introduction and exploration of a 'trigger' concept, defined as immediate, clearly perceivable gestures (such as stopping or raising the head) indicating the precise moment of onset. Our findings suggest a dual-cue system: preparatory cues broadly predict onset timing, while precise triggers refine the exact onset. We compared the time difference between the predicted and piano onsets with the flute-piano asynchronies and verified the concepts of cue and trigger through expert interviews. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of the complex phenomena of musical cues during performance through multimodal analysis. This paper provides an open-access cue dataset, which can be found on the accompanying website.¹

1. INTRODUCTION

Music performance is inherently multimodal, combining sound and motion. Although these elements primarily convey musical expression to audiences [1], they also play a critical role in ensemble synchronization among performers [2]. Performers often employ specific gestures and breathing sounds as musical cues to synchronize their note onsets, particularly at the beginning or during critical moments in a performance. The convention of cueing approx-

imately one beat before the musical onset has been extensively documented in previous studies [3–5]. Head nodding gestures, in particular, are commonly used as intuitive musical cues, and previous studies have utilized such gestures to define cue timings, even extending their application to interactions with robotic musicians [5–7]. Therefore, understanding musical cues not only deepens synchronization knowledge but is also crucial for designing interactive performance systems.

Previous studies have examined the role of gestures and breathing in performer synchronization. Bishop et al. showed that performers use visual and auditory cues to synchronize after silence or rests [8]. Additionally, gestures at the beginning of a piece were found to correlate with tempo, particularly through falling acceleration curves that typically reach their midpoint approximately one beat before the onset [9]. However, this midpoint timing was often not precisely one beat ahead, and exact onset prediction based on these curves was not explored. Vera et al. demonstrated increased onset asynchrony when performers restarted together after rests without visual contact, and identified relationships between breath onset-offset timings and rest durations, yet did not clarify how gestures or breathing specifically encode onset timing [10]. Although these studies highlight the significance of gestures and breath cues in synchronization, they have not thoroughly investigated how combined visual and auditory cues precisely predict intended onset timing, especially at the beginning of a piece.

One reason for the limited quantitative analyses in previous studies is the difficulty of accurately tracking gestures. Bishop et al. utilized Kinect sensors and accelerometers to measure motion curves [9], while Timmers et al. employed infrared markers to measure bow velocity in a string quartet setting [11]. In contrast, our approach uses sensorless image processing techniques, applying optical flow methods [12] to quantitatively track facial gesture movements.

This paper investigates how a flutist's intended onset timing is encoded through gesture and breath cues, comprising four main components: (1) Collection of synchronized video and audio data from flute-piano duet performances involving 20 flutists (Total 1,320 trials), (2) Extraction and annotation of gesture cue features using face movement curves analyzed by optical flow, alongside manual annotation of breath onset and offset timings, (3) Verification of predictive accuracy for cue-based onset pre-

¹ https://github.com/jaeranchoi/flutist_cue_dataset

Figure 1: The overall framework for the musical cue detection and onset timing prediction

84 ditions by comparing linear regression–derived timings to 129
 85 observed human onset asynchronies and (4) Exploration of 130
 86 a trigger concept, which involves three types of immediate, 131
 87 clearly perceivable movements: quickly raising the head, 132
 88 stopping head movement after the cue or slowly raising the 133
 89 head. The first type just before fully raising the head, the 134
 90 second triggers onset immediately after stopping, and the 135
 91 third provides a less clear signal. These trigger movements 136
 92 allow performers to precisely detect the onset moment for 137
 93 accurate synchronization. 138

94 Our analysis demonstrates clear relationships between 139
 95 the lengths of gesture and breath cues and onset timings. 140
 96 Gesture cues showed a linear relationship between po- 141
 97 sition, velocity and acceleration peaks in vertical facial 142
 98 movements and subsequent onset timing. Similarly, breath 143
 99 cues exhibited a correlation between breath duration and 144
 100 the timing interval to the note onset, with variations ob- 145
 101 served across different tempos. We further verified our hy- 146
 102 potheses through expert interviews. Additionally, we con- 147
 103 ducted a case study to address related phenomena, includ- 148
 104 ing adaptation effects—reduced discrepancies through re- 149
 105 peated rehearsal—and instances of cue execution failures, 150
 106 where significant differences between cue-based predicted 151
 107 onset and actual onset were observed. Based on these 152
 108 observations, we conclude that musicians utilize two pri- 153
 109 mary synchronization strategies: rough timing indication 154
 110 through gesture and breath cues, and precise, immediate 155
 111 signals through triggers. Furthermore, exact synchroniza- 156
 112 tion is refined through repetitive rehearsals. 157
 158

113 **2. RELATED WORKS**

114 **2.1 Musical Cue for Synchronization** 159

115 Musical cues, essential for performer communication, 160
 116 include visual gestures and non-musical elements like 161
 117 breathing. They are particularly valuable for precise coor- 162
 118 dination, such as in pieces with abrupt tempo changes [13], 163
 119 or synchronization after rests and tempo variations [8]. 164
 120 The beginning of a musical piece is challenging for coordi- 165
 121 nation due to the absence of preceding audio cues. Bishop 166
 122 et al. examined visual cues at piece initiation, finding that 167
 123 the peak of the acceleration curve in nodding gestures indi- 168
 124 cated beat positions, while gesture duration and periodicity 169
 125 conveyed tempo information [9]. However, they did not in- 170
 126 vestigate the predictive capability of gesture cues for onset 171
 127 timing prediction. 172

128 Most studies on synchronization between gestures and

musical rhythm have emphasized velocity peaks rather than spatial positions as primary features. Su [14] demonstrated this using minimal laboratory setups with bouncing point-light and auditory stimuli. Similar findings emerged from string quartet studies linking bow speed to tempo cues [11], and conductor studies emphasizing baton velocity and acceleration [15]. Vera et al. further highlighted breath cues’ significance in synchronization, particularly when visual contact is limited [10]. These studies underline the role of gesture and breath cues in synchronization, suggesting velocity, acceleration, and cue length influence timing. However, few studies have simultaneously examined those cues in wind instruments to assess their impact on timing. Our study extends this by quantitatively examining correlations between gestures, breath cues, and onset timings through multimodal analysis of flute-piano duets.

2.2 Gesture Analysis of Performance

Motion tracking methods utilizing sensors or optical flow-based video tracking [16] are common for gesture analysis. Previous studies by Bishop et al. and Timmers et al. used attachable sensors or markers to measure movement and acceleration [9, 11], whereas Bochen et al. applied audio-visual analysis with optical flow to examine vibrato patterns from string players’ hand movements [17, 18]. Maezawa et al. proposed MuEns, a multimodal score-following system employing optical flow to track gestures for automated piano accompaniment. However, in that particular work, the authors utilized arbitrarily defined gesture cues instead of systematically analyzing how performers naturally encode onset timings [5].

3. DATASET

3.1 Musical Cue Dataset

We created a multimodal cue dataset containing video and audio recordings of flute-piano duet performances to analyze musical cues from gestures and breathing sounds. Following previous studies [9, 14], we identified peaks in position, velocity, and acceleration curves as potential gesture cue points. Breath cue points were defined by the breath onset and offset timings. We termed the interval between paired cue points as ‘cue length’ and the duration from cue initiation to flute onset as ‘cue-onset length’.

3.1.1 Participants

A total of 20 professional flutists and 3 pianists participated in the experiment, all holding bachelor’s or master’s

Figure 2: Breath Cue and Onset Annotation Breath cue is defined by the breath onset and offset annotated on the mel spectrogram. Six markers are annotated per trial. Detailed information can be found in Section 3.2

173 degrees in performance. Each flutist-pianist pair had not
 174 previously performed together.

175 **3.1.2 Placement and Equipment**

176 The setup mimicked a concert stage, with flutists positioned
 177 facing away from the pianists. The pianists could
 178 observe the flutists, while the flutists were instructed to
 179 give cues without turning or looking at the pianists. A
 180 camera recorded flutists at 60 fps², and microphones separately
 181 captured audio from each instrument at 44.1 kHz.
 182 A neutral-colored screen behind flutists minimized back-
 183 ground interference for accurate facial movement tracking.

184 **3.1.3 Musical Piece**

185 This dataset comprises simultaneously starting flute-piano
 186 duets. Part 1 included a C major scale and Pachelbel's
 187 Canon performed at slow (50 BPM), medium (100 BPM)
 188 and fast (150 BPM) tempos, each repeated twice as warm-
 189 up exercises (12 trials). Part 2 consisted of 18 classical
 190 pieces simplified for piano and arranged for simultaneous
 191 starts. Each piece was assigned a specific tempo (50, 100,
 192 or 150 BPM), and the entire set of 18 pieces was repeated
 193 three times, resulting in 54 trials. Each duet performed a
 194 total of 66 trials, resulting in 1,320 trials overall. Sheet
 195 music and sample audio were provided in advance.

196 **3.1.4 Procedure**

197 The recording procedure for each piece included: (1) An
 198 experimenter's clap signaling start, followed by a measure
 199 of clicks matching the given tempo; (2) The flutist giving a
 200 cue after clicks ended; (3) The duet beginning in response
 201 to the cue.

202 **3.1.5 Post-session Interview**

203 The interviews collected the insights of the participants
 204 on cue strategies. Participants reported providing cues ap-
 205 proximately one beat (or half or two beats, depending on
 206 the piece) ahead, using body movements or breath. Some
 207 participants mentioned that in typical performance situa-
 208 tions, they adjust their cue timing based on the accompa-
 209 nying instrument and ensemble context.

² Some videos were recorded at 30 fps due to camera overheating

Figure 3: Gesture Cue Example Gesture cue is defined with the maximum (red) and minimum (black) peaks. The interval between these peaks, called 'cue length' (x , red line), and the duration between the maximum peak to the flute onset, called 'cue-onset length' (y , blue line).

210 **3.2 Annotation and Preprocessing**

211 Video and audio data synchronization was achieved
 212 through an experimenter's clap at the start. Using the spec-
 213 trogram viewer in Adobe Audition, we manually annotated
 214 six markers per trial on the mel spectrogram (Figure 2): the
 215 experimenter's clap (*Start*), breath sound onset and offset
 216 (*Breath Onset*, *Breath Offset*), initial note onsets of flute
 217 and piano (*Flute Onset*, *Piano Onset*), and the flute's sec-
 218 ond measure onset (*2nd Measure*).

219 **4. METHODS**

220 **4.1 Gesture Cue Detection**

221 **4.1.1 Motion Detection**

222 To detect gesture cues from flutists, we used MediaPipe's
 223 face landmark detection³ [19] to reliably identify face re-
 224 gions, even when partially obscured by the flute. Subse-
 225 quently, optical flow methods [17, 18] were applied to track
 226 facial motion. A pilot study indicated optimal face land-
 227 mark detection accuracy when the face occupied at least
 228 50% of the video frame height; videos were accordingly
 229 resized.

230 **4.1.2 Motion Feature Extraction**

231 We analyzed facial gestures by extracting position, veloc-
 232 ity, and acceleration magnitude curves from averaged y -
 233 axis optical flow values. Due to quantized pixel positions
 234 causing discrete velocity curves, we applied zero-phase fil-
 235 tering⁴ to smooth the curve while preserving peak posi-
 236 tions.

237 **4.1.3 Motion Peak Picking**

238 Figure 3 illustrates a typical gesture cue pattern. Within a
 239 one-measure window preceding the flute onset ('cue win-
 240 dow'), we identified maximum and minimum peaks on
 241 position, velocity, and acceleration curves using the *find-*
 242 *peaks*⁵ algorithm. This approach automatically detected

³ available at: <https://developers.google.com/mediapipe>

⁴ `scipy.signal.filtfilt`

⁵ `scipy.signal.find_peaks`

Figure 4: Relationship between Cue Length and Cue-Onset Length for Gesture Position, Velocity, Acceleration, and Breath Cue Black line: overall regression; blue, green, pink: 50, 100, 150 BPM, respectively. Slopes ($y = ax$) and correlation (r) are shown for each curve.

243 848 peaks, with 394 manually annotated. Trials without
 244 clear peak patterns or failed tracking were excluded, re-
 245 sulting in 1,242 usable trials out of 1,320. Gesture curves
 246 from cases where peak tracking failed are also available on
 247 the accompanying webpage.

248 **4.2 Breath Cue Detection**

249 To detect breath cues, we annotated breath onset and offset
 250 within the same one-measure ‘cue window’ preceding flute
 251 onset, based on mel spectrograms (Figure 2). Analyses
 252 were conducted exclusively on the 1,242 trials that were
 253 verified to contain valid gesture cues.

254 **4.3 Onset Timing Prediction**

255 We examined four cues: gesture position, velocity, accel-
 256 eration, and breath. To explore the relationship between
 257 these cues and onset timing, we applied a simple linear
 258 regression model. Each cue length was set as the inde-
 259 pendent variable x , while the cue-onset length (the inter-
 260 val from cue start positions—maximum peak or breath on-
 261 set—to the actual onset) was the dependent variable y . The
 262 regression model, without bias, is defined by $y=ax$, as il-
 263 lustrated in Figure 3. The slope a derived from the
 264 regression indicates the ratio between cue length and onset
 265 timing, enabling onset prediction. Additionally, we ana-
 266 lyzed the trials separately by tempo to assess differences
 267 in cue-onset relationships, examining both the regression
 268 slope and Pearson correlation. A high correlation would
 269 confirm the cue’s validity for predicting onset timing.

270 **5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

271 **5.1 Patterns in Gesture Curves**

272 The position curve did not consistently show the same
 273 shape in all trials, but in most cases it remained static ini-
 274 tially and then displayed a clear downward-up-down mo-
 275 tion pattern that served as a signal (Figure 3). Even when
 276 the position curve deviated from the typical pattern, an
 277 up-down motion immediately preceding onset was consis-
 278 tently present (1242 out of 1320 trials, see Section 4.1.3).
 279 These movements were often periodic and sinusoidal, re-
 280 sulting in velocity and acceleration curves that mirrored
 281 the position curve, but phase-shifted by approximately a
 282 quarter cycle. Further investigation could examine how
 283 variations in curve characteristics, such as the degree of si-
 284 nusoidal shape and periodicity consistency, influence per-

formers’ interpretation of cues and their subsequent syn-
 chronization accuracy. Moreover, analyzing deviations
 from typical sinusoidal patterns might uncover additional
 insights into performer-specific gesture strategies. Due to
 challenges in quantifying these curve characteristics pre-
 cisely, this topic remains open for future research.

289 **5.2 Results of the Linear Regression**

290 Figure 4 illustrates the relationships between cue length
 291 and cue-onset length for gesture and breath cues across all
 292 participants. Both types of cues showed linear relation-
 293 ships with cue-onset durations. For breath cues, eight out-
 294 liers were identified due to ambiguous annotations; these
 295 were excluded from subsequent regression analyses. Lin-
 296 ear regression indicated slopes of 1.53 (gesture position),
 297 2.28 (gesture velocity), 3.05 (gesture acceleration), and
 298 1.78 (breath cue). Interestingly, none of the cues yielded
 299 a slope close to 2, suggesting that counting the cue length
 300 and subsequent duration as equal units (similar to count-
 301 ing two beats) is not consistently applicable. The veloc-
 302 ity and breath cues had slopes closest to 2, but the in-
 303 terval from the velocity cue to onset was slightly longer
 304 (1.28 times cue length), while for the breath cue it was
 305 slightly shorter (0.78 times cue length). Gesture accelera-
 306 tion showed a strong correlation (0.72) with cue-onset du-
 307 rations, but breath cues exhibited an even stronger correla-
 308 tion (0.78), highlighting their superior reliability for pre-
 309 dicting onsets. The higher correlation with velocity and ac-
 310 celeration compared to position aligns with previous stud-
 311 ies, suggesting performers primarily perceive velocity or
 312 acceleration peaks as cue indicators rather than positional
 313 points. However, acceleration peaks closely align with pre-
 314 vious position peaks, indicating a potential two-peak en-
 315 coding pattern in position curves. Precisely quantifying
 316 this relationship is challenging and thus remains a topic
 317 for future research.

Additionally, slopes generally decreased slightly with
 increased tempo, indicating flute onsets occurred sooner
 than expected based on proportionally shortened cue
 lengths. Furthermore, correlation coefficients for gesture
 cues decreased at higher tempos, whereas breath cues ex-
 hibited higher correlations at faster tempos, reinforcing the
 effectiveness of breath cues for synchronization.

Figure 5: Histogram of Note Onset Asynchrony Onset time differences between the pianist’s onset and 1. Flutist onset (Ground truth) 2-4. Predicted onset from gesture position, velocity, acceleration cue 5. Predicted onset from breath cue.

ID	Group	Gesture Clarity	Onset Timing	Breath Clarity	Onset Timing	Async	Abs Async	STD
A	late	4.5	3.3	3.9	3.4	71	71	39
	good	4.0	3.6	4.8	3.0	54	54	31
	fast	3.8	2.4	4.4	2.6	-54	125	66
B	late	4.4	3.1	3.9	3.1	71	71	39
	good	3.1	3.4	3.3	3.4	54	54	31
	fast	3.9	3.9	4.5	3.9	-54	125	66

Table 1: Result of the Expert Evaluation Expert ratings of cue clarity and execution timing (1 = late, 3 = on-time, 5 = early) on a 5-point scale, with asynchrony metrics (ms) indicating average group asynchrony.

Figure 6: Human onset asynchrony across session repetition.

As described in Section 3.1.3, we observed asynchrony changes through an initial warm-up session of 12 trials (S1) and three repeated sets of 18 pieces (T1–T3), illustrated in Figure 6. Asynchrony notably decreased from the initial warm-up session (S1) through the second repetition session (T2) but stabilized thereafter. We interpret this as indicating adaptation effects, where performers quickly improved synchronization by familiarizing themselves with each other’s cues. However, ongoing piece variation and unresolved consensus about triggers (Section 5.4) likely prevented further reduction in asynchrony beyond a certain threshold.

5.4 Triggers

Despite the considerable accuracy of linear predictions (Section 5.2), questions remained regarding precise cue recognition, particularly for velocity and acceleration peaks. Given potential perception errors in identifying cue points, we investigated additional factors musicians might use to ensure precise synchronization. We observed characteristic gesture patterns immediately following cue movements near onset timings. After the downward-upward-downward cue motion, flutists typically executed one of three distinct trigger patterns (Figure 7): (A) initiating onset just before raising the head again, typically aligned with the previous upward cue movement, (B) briefly pausing with the head lowered and starting immediately afterward, or (C) ambiguously initiating onset while slowly raising the head. Patterns (A) and (B) provided clear, immediate signals suitable as precise triggers. Pattern (C), however, represented ambiguous or absent triggers. Without prior agreement, these ambiguous gestures could cause confusion—for example, a flutist intending pattern (A) might be misinterpreted by the pianist as pattern (B), resulting in significant timing discrepancies. Such cases were indeed observed, and the validity of these trigger patterns was further confirmed through expert interviews (Section 5.5). Thus, we propose that musicians initially encode approximate timing through cues and then

5.3 Note Onset Asynchrony

5.3.1 Asynchrony Comparison

Figure 5 shows histograms of time differences between the pianist’s onset and five conditions: actual flutist onset (gray) and four predicted onsets from the linear regression model (Section 5.2). This error represents the discrepancy expected if the flutist perfectly followed our linear model and executed the cues precisely. A notable feature in the pianist-flutist asynchrony histogram is the minimal occurrence of trials just before zero milliseconds. This suggests a tendency for the leader (flutist) to start slightly earlier than the follower (pianist), aligning with observations confirmed by expert interviews (Section 5.5.2). Additionally, we consider auditory reaction (performers starting in response to hearing the partner’s onset) unlikely in most cases, as the observed asynchronies are typically smaller than the average auditory reaction time (150 ms) [20].

The ‘Pianist-Flutist asynchrony’ had the narrowest spread (Absolute(Abs) mean = 79ms, Standard Deviation (STD) = 168ms), consistent with previous research reporting the first onset asynchronies slightly above 80ms [9]. Gesture-based predictions showed absolute mean errors between 121–168ms, with acceleration predictions exhibiting higher variability (STD = 247ms). Breath predictions were more consistent (Abs mean = 109 ms, STD = 209 ms). Although the acceleration cue demonstrated the highest Pearson correlation, its greater variability and longer cue length contributed to larger errors. These findings suggest that while cue-based linear predictions are slightly less precise than human synchronization, breath cues provide more reliable predictions than gesture-based cues. The precision of predictions compared with actual flutist onsets exhibited similar patterns.

5.3.2 Reduction of Asynchrony Through Repetition

We also investigated whether synchronization accuracy improves as pianists and flutists adapt to each other’s cues.

Figure 7: Examples of three trigger types (A, B, C) Green dashed lines indicate breath onset and offset, the blue line marks flute onset, and the red line piano onset. The red shaded area represents the cue interval.

401 achieve precise synchronization through clearly defined
402 trigger gestures.

403 5.5 Expert Evaluation and Interview

404 After the main analysis, we conducted a two-hour inter-
405 view with two expert flutists, each with over 20 years of
406 ensemble and teaching experience. The session involved
407 two main tasks: evaluating trials categorized as fast, good,
408 or late based on onset predictions from velocity cues, and
409 assessing our trigger hypothesis. Due to time constraints,
410 only velocity cues were used, as they offered the most in-
411 terpretable and perceptually reliable basis for cue classifica-
412 tion.

413 5.5.1 Evaluation of Linear Model Predictions

414 Experts reviewed 8 trials from each group (fast, good, late)
415 to evaluate the clarity of the cues (accuracy) and whether
416 the actual onset timing matched the timing implied by the
417 cue (execution timing). The experts evaluated 24 randomly
418 ordered trials without being informed of the group labels.
419 After agreeing with the assumption that head-nodding ges-
420 tures and breathing serve as cues, experts rated cue accu-
421 racy on a scale from 1 (no recognizable cue) to 5 (clearly
422 recognizable cue) and execution timing from 1 (very late)
423 to 5 (very early), with 3 representing precise timing. Re-
424 sults are summarized in Table 1.

425 Surprisingly, the experts differed notably in their eval-
426 uations of breath cue execution timing, which also did not
427 align clearly with actual pianist-flutist asynchrony. Expert
428 A rated the ‘good’ group’s gesture cues as slightly late but
429 breath cues as most accurate. Expert B rated the groups in
430 descending order (late-good-fast) of perceived lateness but
431 still considered the ‘late’ group relatively early (average
432 3.1). Actual asynchrony partly aligned with our predic-
433 tions; the ‘good’ group exhibited the smallest asynchrony,
434 consistent with the cue hypothesis. However, unexpected
435 discrepancies emerged, such as the ‘fast’ group showed
436 later flute onsets than the piano. These inconsistencies
437 likely reflect individual variations in interpreting and ex-
438 ecuting cues.

439 5.5.2 In-depth Interview

440 After the video evaluation, we conducted detailed discus-
441 sions about the linear prediction model and the trigger
442 concept. Experts acknowledged the general practice of
443 cueing approximately one beat ahead, noting that specific

444 movements were intuitively executed rather than explic-
445 itly planned. Both emphasized tempo-related influences on
446 gesture and breath cues, highlighting gesture periodicity as
447 crucial for clear cue delivery.

448 Regarding triggers, experts initially did not consciously
449 recognize different trigger types but agreed with the pro-
450 posed classifications after reviewing examples. Both
451 agreed type (A) was optimal, while type (B) was con-
452 sidered challenging due to the flute’s physical constraints.
453 Opinions on type (C) diverged: Expert A considered it in-
454 herently prone to higher errors, whereas Expert B believed
455 it could be viable when accompanied by precise breath
456 cues and rehearsal. Experts noted that triggers may vary
457 depending on musical context (phrasing, emphasis). They
458 also observed potential triggers, including the flute’s end-
459 point position, lip shape, and finger movements. Finally,
460 both proposed that in flute-piano duets, slight delays in pi-
461 ano onset might cognitively benefit synchronization, po-
462 tentially explaining the scarcity of trials where piano onset
463 preceded flute onset, as observed in Figure 5.

464 5.6 Limitation

465 Although this study contributes to understanding cue-
466 based synchronization, several limitations remain. First,
467 our trigger analysis was not fully quantitative; future re-
468 search should develop precise methods for defining trig-
469 gers from gesture curves and consider additional signals
470 such as lip shape, finger movements, and horizontal flute
471 actions. Second, The decision-making process for select-
472 ing triggers was not investigated. Exploring how musi-
473 cians choose and agree on triggers could further clarify
474 synchronization strategies. Additionally, individual vari-
475 ability in cue and trigger preferences was not quantitatively
476 examined; future research could explore personalized syn-
477 chronization strategies. Lastly, our findings apply specifi-
478 cally to flute-piano duets and piece initiation. Generalizing
479 these methods to other instrument combinations and ongo-
480 ing musical contexts remains necessary.

481 6. CONCLUSION

482 This study investigated how gesture and breath cues used
483 by flutists in flute-piano duets encode note onset timing at
484 the initiation of musical pieces. To quantitatively analyze
485 cues, we collected a cue dataset, identifying cue points via
486 motion tracking and breath sounds. Our multimodal anal-
487 ysis revealed linear relationships between cue lengths and
488 onset timings, confirming that gesture and breath cues re-
489 liably predict onset timing. In addition, we introduced the
490 concept of triggers, defined as immediate gestures that in-
491 dicate precise onset moments, which we validated through
492 expert interviews. Future research could further develop
493 the analysis of triggers to achieve a more systematic un-
494 derstanding. Additionally, developing regression models
495 that jointly use gesture and breath cues, or exploring so-
496 phisticated predictive models, would be valuable. It could
497 further extend our cue analysis methods to other instru-
498 ments, ensemble configurations, and within-performance
499 synchronization, providing deeper insights into the com-
500 plexity of ensemble coordination.

7. ETHICS STATEMENT

This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB), and all participants consented to video recording and data sharing. Each flutist’s session lasted 1.5 hours, pianists had 30-minute breaks between sessions, with up to four sessions per day. Participants received appropriate compensation. To protect privacy, the video data will remain confidential.

8. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has been supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) grant funded by the Korea government (MSIT) under Grant RS-2023-NR077289 and Grant RS-2024-00358448.

9. REFERENCES

[1] C.-J. Tsay, “Sight over sound in the judgment of music performance,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 110, no. 36, pp. 14 580–14 585, 2013.

[2] L. Bishop, C. Cancino-Chacón, and W. Goebel, “Moving to communicate, moving to interact: Patterns of body motion in musical duo performance,” *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 1–25, 2019.

[3] F. K. Hukporti, *Your Guide to Basic Conducting*. Acra: Noyam Publishers, 2023.

[4] R. Page-Shipp, D. Joseph, and C. van Niekerk, “Conductorless singing group: a particular kind of self-managed team?” *Team Performance Management: An International Journal*, vol. 24, no. 5/6, pp. 331–346, 2018.

[5] A. Maezawa and K. Yamamoto, “MuEns: A multi-modal human-machine music ensemble for live concert performance,” in *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2017, pp. 4290–4301.

[6] X. Gao, A. Rogel, R. Sankaranarayanan, B. Dowling, and G. Weinberg, “Music, body, and machine: gesture-based synchronization in human-robot musical interaction,” *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, vol. 11, 2024.

[7] A. Lim, T. Mizumoto, L.-K. Cahier, T. Otsuka, T. Takahashi, K. Komatani, T. Ogata, and H. G. Okuno, “Robot musical accompaniment: integrating audio and visual cues for real-time synchronization with a human flutist,” in *2010 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, 2010, pp. 1964–1969.

[8] L. Bishop and W. Goebel, “When they listen and when they watch: Pianists’ use of nonverbal audio and visual cues during duet performance,” *Musicae Scientiae*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 84–110, 2015.

[9] ———, “Beating time: How ensemble musicians’ cueing gestures communicate beat position and tempo,” *Psychology of Music*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 84–106, 2018.

[10] B. Vera, E. Chew, and P. G. Healey, “A study of ensemble synchronisation under restricted line of sight.” in *International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference (ISMIR)*, 2013, pp. 293–298.

[11] R. Timmers, S. Endo, A. Bradbury, and A. M. Wing, “Synchronization and leadership in string quartet performance: a case study of auditory and visual cues,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 5, p. 645, 2014.

[12] B. Li, X. Liu, K. Dinesh, Z. Duan, and G. Sharma, “Creating a multitrack classical music performance dataset for multimodal music analysis: Challenges, insights, and applications,” *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 522–535, 2018.

[13] S. Kawase, “Gazing behavior and coordination during piano duo performance,” *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, vol. 76, pp. 527–540, 2014.

[14] Y.-H. Su, “Audiovisual beat induction in complex auditory rhythms: Point-light figure movement as an effective visual beat,” *Acta Psychologica*, vol. 151, pp. 40–50, 2014.

[15] G. Luck and J. A. Sloboda, “Spatio-temporal cues for visually mediated synchronization,” *Music Perception*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 465–473, 2009.

[16] B. K. Horn and B. G. Schunck, “Determining optical flow,” *Artificial intelligence*, vol. 17, no. 1-3, pp. 185–203, 1981.

[17] B. Li, K. Dinesh, Z. Duan, and G. Sharma, “See and listen: Score-informed association of sound tracks to players in chamber music performance videos,” in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2017, pp. 2906–2910.

[18] B. Li, C. Xu, and Z. Duan, “Audiovisual source association for string ensembles through multi-modal vibrato analysis,” *Proc. Sound and Music Computing (SMC)*, pp. 159–166, 2017.

[19] V. Bazarevsky, I. Grishchenko, K. Raveendran, T. Zhu, F. Zhang, and M. Grundmann, “Blazepose: On-device real-time body pose tracking,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.10204*, 2020.

[20] R. J. Kosinski, “A literature review on reaction time,” *Clemson University*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 337–344, 2008.